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STUDY OF RATIONAL PRESCRIBING PATTERN AND DRUG MANAGEMENT FOR GERIATRIC PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: The aim of this study was to rationalize the prescribing pattern and drug management in geriatric patients. **METHODS:** This prospective study comprised a convenience sample of 150 cases related to geriatric patients admitted to Saptagiri hospital. **RESULTS:** In our 150 cases, 57% were females and 43% were males. Among them, 66% of patients were reported to have 2 diseases, 24% of patients were diagnosed with 3 disease while patients having >3 diseases were reported to be 10%. The chronic cases of diseases related to hypertension and diabetes were counted to be greater in frequency (DM: 23%, HTN: 49%, DM+HTN: 28%). Amlodipine (5mg) was prescribed rationally for most of the hypertensive patients. Along with that, Human Actrapid (Insulin) and Metformin (oral hypoglycemic agent) was prescribed rationally for more number of diabetic patients. **CONCLUSION:** This result emphasized the rational use of geriatric medicine mostly related to the chronic condition of hypertension and diabetes. It shows the acceptability and tolerability of drugs prescribed for geriatric individuals.

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INTRODUCTION

Geriatrics refers to medical care for older adults, an age group that is not easy to define precisely. "Older" is preferred over "elderly," but both are equally imprecise; > 65 is the age often used, but most people do not need geriatrics expertise in **their care** until age 70, 75, or even 80. Gerontology is the study of aging, including biologic, sociologic, and psychological changes. The effects of aging must be taken into account during the diagnosis and treatment of older adults. Clinicians should not

- Mistake pure aging for disease (eg, slow information retrieval is not dementia)
- Mistake disease for pure aging (eg, ascribe debilitating arthritis, tremor, or dementia to old age)
- Ignore the increased risk of adverse drug effects on weak-link systems stressed by illness
- Forget that older adults often have multiple underlying disorders (eg, hypertension, diabetes, atherosclerosis) that accelerate the potential for harm.

INDIAN SCENARIO OF ELDERLY PEOPLE

ICMR (Indian Council Of Medical research) report on the chronic morbidity profile in the elderly states that the hearing impairment is the most common morbidity followed by visual impairment.

Morbidity studies in Pondicherry's rural area reported the following medical conditions in patients 60 and above:-

1. Decreased visual activity due to cataract (57%)
2. Pain and stiffness in joints (43.4%)
3. Chewing complaints (42%)
4. Hearing impairment (15.4%)
5. Hypertension (14%)
6. Diarrhea (12%)
7. Chronic cough (12%)
8. Skin diseases (12%)
9. Heart diseases (9%)
10. Diabetes (8.1%)
11. Asthma (6%)
12. Urinary Complaints (5.6%)

NEED FOR STUDY

In geriatric patients, the vital physiological functions decline as ageing occurs. It is of utmost importance to prevent and investigate complications associated with polypharmacy such as drug interactions and adverse drug reactions, to check irrational use of medications and to investigate whether the prescribed dose is appropriate and follows standard geriatric guidelines.

METHODOLOGY

AIM:

Study the rational prescribing pattern and drug management for geriatric patients in tertiary care hospital.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

The objective of present study are:

Primary objective:

To evaluate rational drug use of medications in hospitalized geriatric patients in a tertiary care hospital for the patients 60 years and above.

Secondary objective:

1. To assess the prescribing pattern of geriatric patients.
2. To enhance the quality of life of the elderly patients.
3. To determine complications related to polypharmacy.
4. To evaluate most preferred category of medications that were prescribed for various diseases in the geriatric age group.

DURATION OF STUDY

The study will be conducted for a period of six months.

SITE OF STUDY

The study will be conducted at Saphthagiri General Hospital.

STUDY DESIGN

A hospital based retrospective and prospective observational study.

SOURCES OF DATA AND MATERIALS

Patient case sheet
Laboratory data reports
Medication / treatment chart
Suitable design documentation form

STUDY CRITERIA**Inclusion criteria**

Patients 60 years and above are included in this criteria.

Exclusion criteria

Patients who were unconscious, admitted to ICU and outpatients were excluded from the study.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1. Data collection form:
2. Data will collected by using a self-designed data collection form, which consists of details like patient demographics, laboratory data, drug therapy and other relevant information.
3. Patient Medical Record:
4. Data will collected from Patient Medical Record which comprised of patient demographics, history of patient, general physical examination, laboratory data, and drug therapy.

STUDY PROCEDURE

This is a retrospective and prospective observational study, the patients who are satisfying the inclusion criteria will be enrolled into the study with the help of patient consent form. The clinical pharmacist will review the patient case notes, medication chart, laboratory data and other prevalent data.

A structured data collection form will be used to record all the necessary data including patient demographic details, patient medication history, co morbid conditions and reason for admission, medication details and lab investigation. The pattern of drug dosing will be recorded.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis was performed using MS excel and the result was statistically analyzed using appropriate statistical method like bar diagrams, pie charts etc.

RESULTS

The case reports of 150 patients above 60 years has been collected and studied in Saptagiri hospital in various wards giving the results as below:

TABLE I :- GENDER CLASSIFICATION.

Total Male	65
Total Female	85
Total Case	150

FIG.I.

The figure above shows total number of males vs females out of 150 patients studied.65males have been reported along with 85 females diagnosed with various chronic diseases among geriatric age groups.

TABLE II:- AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION.

Age	Number
60-65	42
65-70	46
70-75	28
75-80	20
80-85	14

FIG.II.

The bar diagram shows the results of various age group vs the number of patients admitted to the hospital. Above investigation shows that maximum number of patients were admitted between the age group 65-70 whereas least number patients reported between age group 80-85.

TABLE III:- LENGTH OF STAY.

Length of stay	Number of patients
0-5 days	36
5-10 days	50
10-15 days	49
>15 days	15

FIG : III:

Maximum inpatients were admitted in the hospital for a period of 5-10 days and 10-15 days. The survey showed minimum number of admissions in the inpatients for more than 15 days or above.

TABLE IV:- COMPLICATIONS.

Complications	Number of cases
2 diseases	33
3 diseases	12
>3 diseases	5

FIG IV:-

Pie-chart has been created for co-morbidities results. Out of 50 cases, 2 diseases results more in number as compared to 3 or more than 3 diseases.

Hypertension and diabetes has been occurred more in number than any other age related diseases. Bone related diseases like Osteoarthritis and pulmonary diseases like asthma and COPD occurs frequently after Diabetes and Hypertension.

TABLE V:- PREVALANT DISEASES.

CLASSIFICATION	NUMBER OF CASES
Complications	50
Ophthalmology	9
Orthopedics	20
CVS diseases	18
Dermatology	7
Liver disease	6
Renal disease	5
Hematology	6
Psychiatry	4
GIT	6
Infectious disease	7
Pulmonary	8
CNS	4

CLASSIFICATION	MOST OBSERVED DISEASE
Ophthalmology	-Cataract -Decreased vision
Orthopedics	-rheumatoid arthritis -osteoarthritis -Fracture -Lumbar disk disease
CV Diseases	- Stroke -Accelerated hypertension -IHD -MI -Diabetes Mellitus
Dermatology	-Sub acute eczema -Psoriasis
Hepatic	-ALD -Viral hepatitis B -Fatty liver
Renal	-Renal calculus -CKD
Hematology	-Anemia
Psychiatry	-Schizophrenia -GAD -Bipolar disorder with depression
CNS	-Parkinsonism -Insomnia
Pulmonary	-Chronic Bronchitis -LRTI -COPD -Asthma
GIT	-Gastroenteritis
Infectious Disease	-Pulmonary Tuberculosis -Meningitis

FIG V:

Bar diagram above presents different diseases that are diagnosed. Patients diagnosed with more than one disease shows the greatest frequency. However, ortho-related diseases and CVS disease follows the ranking frequency. Patients with pulmonary, ophthalmology and infectious diseases shows equal distribution in the bar diagram.

Some psychiatry and dermatology department related diseases were found in very rare cases. Liver and renal diseased cases were found to be in equal frequency.

TABLE VI:- CHRONIC CONDITIONS.

Chronic conditions	Number of cases
Diabetes Mellitus	9
Hypertension	19
Diabetes mellitus +hypertension	11

FIG VI :

The study of major chronic conditions involved the study of patients with diabetes, hypertension and patients who suffered with both diabetes and hypertension.

Maximum patients (49%) were admitted for hypertension, followed by patients who suffered from combination of diabetes and hypertension (28%).

Only 23% of diabetes mellitus patients were found to be admitted in the study done for chronic cases.

TABLE VII:- MEDICATIONS FOR DM.

Medications for DM	Prescribing Pattern
Human Actrapid	5
Insulin Regular	2
Bosalog	1
Glimepiride	2
Metformin	3
Glibenclamide	2

FIG VII :-

Patients with diabetes mellitus were studied. Medication studies showed the use of Human Actrapid Insulin (short-acting insulin) is used in most of the patients followed by insulin regular (short-acting).

Metformin (Biguanides) was the most used oral hypoglycemic agent followed by Glibenclamide and Glimepiride (Sulfonyl urea).

Long acting insulin analog- Basalog was rarely used.

TABLE VIII:- MEDICATIONS FOR HTN.

Antihypertensive drugs	Prescribing Pattern
Amlodipine	7
Atenolol	3
Metoprolol	6
Propranolol	1
Clinidipine	3
Diltiazem	1
Nifedipine	1
Telmisartan	1
Furosemide	4
Spironolactone	3

FIG VIII:-

Hypertensive patients above 60 years of age have been mostly prescribed with Amlodipine- 5mg (CCB) as the first choice and is recommended throughout their life.

The use of Atenolol, Metoprolol (cardio selective B-blocker), Furosemide (Diuretics) and Clinidipine (CCB) drugs have been used as an adjustment therapy in most complicated cases.

Propranolol, Diltiazem, Telmisartan are rarely used. These drugs are used only in few patients.

TABLE IX:- DM+HTN MEDICATIONS.

DM+HTN Medications	Prescribing patterns
Human Actrapid	2
Human Regular	2
Metformin	6
Glimepiride	1
Amlodipine	4
Cilacar	2
Spironolactone	2
Telmisartan	2
Furosemide	1

TABLE X:-

Number of patients	Medications
48	< / equal to 5
69	6-10
33	>/equal to 11

FIG X:-

From the pie-chart, we can see that maximum of 46% of the patients were administered minimum of 6-10 medications.

More than 11 medications were prescribed to 22% of the patients and only 32% of the total patients received 5 or less than 5 number of medicines.

DISCUSSION

One of the important safety concerns in prescribing practice especially for old people is inappropriate prescription. Inappropriate prescription in elderly patients increase the risk of adverse drug reactions.

Inappropriate prescription is a major concern in countries like India which have a lot of population and logically a lot of geriatric patients among them that may be affected due to inappropriate prescription which causes health issues to the patients and increases the financial burden of the treatment for the patient and the society.

150 cases were collected and studied. According to our investigation, we found out that female age group was more prone to diseases than the male age group.

Results showed 65-70 age group were admitted in the hospital compared to the age group of 60-65 years. The frequency of number of patients in the age group 70-75 resulted same as in the age group of 60-65 years.

The maximum number of days the patient was admitted in a particular ward was for 5-10 days.

Co-morbidities study shown in the pie-chart earlier indicated maximum diagnosis of cases with combination diabetes and hypertension in an individual (66%). Individuals having 3 diseases were 24% and individuals with more than 3 diseases were 10%.

DM and HTN were the most frequent cases studied out of 150 cases. Ortho and CVS related cases were found less in number but more in frequency.

Cases related to Dermatology and pulmonary conditions along with GIT and CNS problems were diagnosed in rare numbers. Medication chart showed the number of antihypertensive drugs and diabetic drugs used were more.

Insulin Human Actrapid and Insulin Regular were more commonly used along with some oral hypoglycemic agents like Glibenclamide and Metformin.

Amlong was found to be the best choice of medication in the patients with early detected high blood pressure. Cardio-selective B-blockers like Atenolol and Metoprolol were prescribed to some of the hypertensive patients.

Maximum number of patients were prescribed with minimum of 6-10 medications per individual. Hence, the case of polypharmacy and the chances of increased drug interaction was abundant.

CONCLUSION

After six months of research and study on rational prescribing pattern and drug management we concluded under prescribing, overprescribing, irrational use of drugs and misprescribing of medications.

Dose of the drugs were given according to adult dose and individualization of dosage regimen was not done. Due to polypharmacy, drug interactions and adverse drug reactions were abundant in number.

Inadequate patient counselling led to decrease in compliance among the patients. Following of treatment guidelines is a major hurdle observed during prescribing of medications in India. Vital physiological functions decline as a result of which toxicity and renal insufficiency was observed.

Hence, to overcome these obstacles, standard and appropriate treatment guidelines must be followed. Geriatric dose calculation and individualization of drug dosage regimen must be done to gain optimum treatment benefits and to reduce complications and mortality rate.

To maintain proper prescribing pattern, Beer's criteria for inappropriate medications must be followed that helps to ensure and improve the prescribing pattern as well as analyze risk and benefit ratio in geriatric population.

Physicians must follow START and STOPP criteria to reduce irrational use of medicines and to minimize potential risk and adverse drug reactions.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION	FULLFORM
DM	DIABETES MELLITUS
HTN	HYPERTENSION
OA	OSTEOARTHRITIS
UTI	URINARY TRACT INFECTION
CKD	CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
IHD	ISCHAEMIC HEART DISEASE
WHO	WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION
ICMR	INDIAN COUNCIL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH
MI	MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION
ALD	ALCOHOLIC LIVER DISEASE
START	SCREENING TOOL TO ALERT DOCTORS TO RIGHT TREATMENT
STOPP	SCREENING TOOL OF OLDER PEOPLE'S POTENTIALLY INAPPROPRIATE PRESCRIPTIONS
%	PERCENTAGE

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